

PROCEEDINGS OF SECOND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INNOVATIONS IN MANAGEMENT, SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND AUTOMATION IN SPORTS

ISBN NUMBER : 978-81-966587-2-4

**DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER SCIENCE
UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY MEGHALAYA**

 India Ranking-2023 (151-200)

Accredited 'A' Grade by NAAC

Campus
Techno City, Khanapara, Kling Road, Baridua, 9th Mile, Ri-Bhoi, Meghalaya- 793101
E-mail : ustm2011@gmail.com Web : www.ustm.ac.in

PROCEEDINGS

Second International Conference on Innovations in Management, Science, Technology and Automation in Sports (ICIMSTAS-2023)

Organized By

**DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER SCIENCE
UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY MEGHALAYA
Techno City, Kling Road, Bariuda, 9th Mile, Ri-Bhoi, Meghalaya**

Second International Conference on Innovations in Management, Science, Technology and Automation in Sports (ICIMSTAS-2023)

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Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use in the Worth of Online Education System in Bangladesh

Motia Mannan¹

¹motiamannn2017@gmail.com

University Tun Abdul Razak (UNIRAZAK)

Tarekol Islam Maruf²

²iiumstarek@gmail.com

International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM)

Abstract

The prevalence of online education has experienced significant growth in tandem with the widespread adoption of digital technology across various domains. The primary factor for transforming the education sector into an entirely virtual format is the significant increase and influence of digitalisation, which accelerated the recent global pandemic. This study examines the perceptions of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use about the value of online education systems while also considering the implications of their adoption in Bangladesh. Furthermore, this study examines the relationship between perceived ease of use and the worth of online education usage, focusing on the mediating role of perceived usefulness. This investigation incorporates the diffusion of technology adoption theory to provide a comprehensive analysis. It examines the broader scope of the online education system, including its perceived usefulness and ease of use. The literature review examines the several components associated with the online education system, focusing on the positive and negative effects of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of online education. This work employs the SEM-AMOES technique to investigate the direct and mediated interactions among the hypothesised components. The sample utilised in this study was obtained through multistage cluster sampling. It consisted of 286 respondents, which was reduced to 265 after screening and sorting due to the presence of partial or missing data. Due to their high population density and diverse cultural characteristics, the study focused on Dhaka, the capital city of Bangladesh. The research sample was selected to ensure representativeness and minimise potential biases by considering several criteria, such as gender, age, and education. The correlation between online education's perceived usefulness and worth has been significant. The findings indicate that each variable evaluated significantly impacts the worth of online education.

Keywords: Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Online Education System in Bangladesh, and technology adoption in online education.

1. Introduction

The online education system is gaining knowledge and skills using distance learning devices and apps. According to Parapi et al. (2020), learning online has mainly evolved and enhanced since its presence after the commercialization of the Internet. Various online sites and platforms have provided the facility for online education. Mouri et al. (2018) commented that the online learning system has supported making the teaching and learning process more seamless. Due to this, learners also obtained the benefit during the recent pandemic period. According to Tabassum et al. (2021), Zoom is the most used online platform in Bangladesh concerning online education, accounting for 58.12%, Skype was 9.03%, and Google Classroom was 9.03%, along with other platforms. The online education system is defined as the procedure of obtaining knowledge and skills through the use of electronic devices. The online education system provides ease of learning and teaching practice for both pupils and teachers (Tartavulea et al., 2020). Online education brings more flexibility to the learning and teaching process. Individuals can learn or get experience from their preferred locations or places. The study aims to understand the impact of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on the online education system in Bangladesh. Online education benefits increase the accessibility of learning for every student. Online education has a positive impact on providing flexibility to students in their learning process (Müller & Mildenerger, 2021). It equally supports more accessible access to learning resources and materials. These two are the key benefits that online education provides to students in their learning process. However, besides these benefits, online education also provides other facilities for students to enhance or get practical knowledge and skills. The online education process benefits from breaking the barrier of communication that learners face in the traditional learning process (Octaberlina & Muslimin, 2020). In online classes, students are not required to show their identity when considering learning and can communicate efficiently without any shyness or nervousness.

On the contrary, the learning challenges equally declined due to the use of online education systems for students. Online education has an adverse influence on students as well. Due to this, student is heavily impacted considering to be competent in their education. According to Selvaraj et al. (2021), online education majorly impacts students based on health. Students feel isolated as they continuously learn without any physical interaction. It equally impacts their mental health to face higher stress.

Similarly, physical health also gets impacted as students do not experience physical activity in their learning process. Another detrimental effect of online learning, according to Rizwan and Kearney (2021), is the educational component, which includes low attendance, a lack of engagement, and poor grades. Similar to this, online schooling raises technological issues. This is because there are a lot of underdeveloped places without internet connectivity and where students need access to technology equipment.

Thus, research on the relationship between perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness and the worth of online education is essential to improve the quality of user experiences online education provides. This study aims to close a partial gap in the body of literature. In light of the discussion

above, this study aims to investigate students' perspectives by assessing the correlation between perceived value, usefulness, and convenience of use of online learning. This investigation's unique quality will fill a gap in current knowledge and significantly contribute to academia.

2. Literature Review

Theoretical approach: Technology acceptance model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a famous theoretical framework for studying user behaviour (Granic&Marangunic, 2019). The concept states that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use can influence an individual's motivation to act (Davis, 1989; Hsu, & Lin, 2022).). As with any technological situation, perceived usefulness and ease of use significantly impact the value or success of an online education system (Alkhawaja et al., 2022). These factors are typically included in the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), a widely used framework in information systems and technology adoption research (Al-Mamary et al., 2023).

3. Selection of Constructs

The efficacy of the online platform can be assessed by instructors and students based on the quality of instruction it provides. According to Hamzah and Kraiger et al. (2022), individuals are more inclined to perceive the online system as advantageous if they believe that it provides educational resources of superior quality, dynamic material, and opportunities for skill development. Al Amin &Greenwood (2018) assert that Bangladesh exhibits a heterogeneous demographic composition with varying degrees of educational access. The online education system's ability to provide access to educational courses, information, and previously unattainable resources will be seen as highly valuable and advantageous. The flexibility of online education might be a beneficial resource in Bangladesh, as numerous students and professionals face busy schedules or geographical constraints (Lockee, 2021). It is likely advantageous to provide an online system that allows individuals to study at their preferred pace and with a sense of fulfilment. Individuals enrolled in educational programmes or employed in professional settings are inclined to place a higher level of importance on the online system if they believe that pursuing online education will enhance their employment opportunities or facilitate career progression.

The construct denoting how individuals perceive technology as adaptable and user-friendly is commonly called "ease of use" (Ulum, 2022). According to Abel-Smith (2018), it is suggested that the online education system in Bangladesh should incorporate a user-friendly interjection as part of its principles. Users are more inclined to engage with a system if they perceive it to possess a user-friendly interface, efficient content retrieval capabilities, and seamless interaction features. The concept of perceived usefulness pertains to individuals' perceptions of the extent to which a specific technology will enhance their job performance or facilitate the completion of tasks (Taharet al., 2020).

Furthermore, it is imperative to provide sufficient technical support and assistance. When consumers encounter technological difficulties and can access support promptly, they regard the

system as more user-friendly. In this regard, the system must exhibit sufficient flexibility to accommodate the unique characteristics of Bangladeshi gadgets and internet access. The presence of challenges related to adaptability can introduce complexities in the context of usability (Albert & Tulis, 2022). According to Alenezi (2020), incorporating training resources and tutorials can enhance the user experience of the online education system, making it more engaging and user-friendly. Language has a crucial role in enhancing usability within the context of Bangladesh. According to Liu et al. (2022), the perceived user-friendliness of the platform can be enhanced by providing support for users with limited proficiency in the English language and by offering availability in regional languages. Evaluating an online education system's value or success is contingent upon consumers' utility and usability judgements in Bangladesh. In order to ensure the success of a system, developers and educators must prioritise many components, such as educational standards, accessibility, user-friendly design, technological support, and compliance with regional expectations and circumstances (Dutta et al., 2020). Enhancing the perceived usefulness and usability can contribute to the long-term success of online education in Bangladesh. These endeavours encompass user testing, usability studies, and feedback-informed continuous development.

4. Perceived Ease of Use

The concept of "ease of use" pertains to the subjective evaluations made by customers regarding the level of simplicity associated with utilising a specific technology (Tahar et al., 2020; Davis, 1989). According to the proposition by Alnagrati et al. (2023), the construct of perceived ease of use can be delineated into four constituent elements: ease of control, simplicity of comprehension, user-friendliness, and access. Several studies conducted by Tahar et al. (2020), and Ji et al. (2019) have revealed the significance of perceived ease of use within the context of online application. The positive and substantial impact of the intention to utilise technology is determined by the perceived ease of use, as indicated by Al-Adwan et al. (2023). The study by Nikou & Maslov (2021) revealed a substantial relationship between perceived ease of use and worth of online education.

In contrast, Demir et al. (2021) found a significant association between worth of online education and users' perception of ease of use. Joo et al. (2018) defines perceived ease of use as the extent to which an individual perceives a specific technology as effortless and instils confidence in its usage. Thus, the relationship can be hypothesized following:

H1: Perceived ease of use has a positive impact on worth of online education.

5. Perceived Usefulness

Perceived usefulness refers to the extent to which an individual believes that utilising an information system will enhance their performance in completing tasks (Davis, 1989). According to the previous research conducted by Chen & Aklikokou (2020), there was a notable and statistically significant association between the perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. This suggests that the perceived usefulness of these apps plays a crucial role in customers' decision-making process, influencing their choice to either engage with or refrain from using app-based

transportation services. Based on the extant literature about perceived usefulness, it has been shown that consumers exhibit a willingness to embrace online application applications because of the perceived ease of use they offer in their daily lives (Faqih, 2022). In a previous investigation conducted by Al-Marouf et al. (2020), it was demonstrated that the perceived usefulness of online applications directly impacts individuals' desire to utilise information systems. According to Maruf et al. (2021), the continuous usage of online education is influenced by individuals' perceived usefulness and ease of use. Perceived usefulness of a technological innovation plays a pivotal role in individuals' decision-making process about its adoption (Caffaro et al., 2020). From the above discussion it can be hypothesized that:

H2: Perceived ease of use has a positive impact on perceived usefulness.

6. Worth of online Education

Online education enables individuals to acquire knowledge or impart instruction from any geographical place. According to Shenkoya & Kim (2023) it might be inferred that there is no obligation to travel or follow a predetermined schedule. Furthermore, it facilitates cost and time efficiency, enabling allocating resources towards other significant endeavours. It addresses the educational requirements or individual learning preferences of students. Besides, online education enhances productivity and proficiency, enhance temporal adaptability and user inclusivity to foster learner engagement in the educational endeavour (Fidalgo et al., 2020). Based on the study conducted by Facts and Factors, it is evident that the global market for online education experienced a substantial expansion, reaching a value of USD 17 billion in 2022. Projections indicate that this market is expected to expand further, reaching a value of USD 475 billion by 2030. This growth is anticipated to be driven by a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of around 9.1% from 2023 to 2030 (Nyhan et al., 2023).

The COVID-19 pandemic has disturbed traditional educational practices, leading students to adopt a more assertive stance in favour of engaging in online learning. Consequently, online education has experienced a notable surge in popularity. The concern expressed is shaped by various factors, such as the perceived level of knowledge, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use of the e-learning platform, and perceived barriers (Fidalgo et al., 2020). The challenges and issues associated with COVID-19 significantly influence students' choices to participate in online education during the pandemic. The pandemic has led to a substantial increase in the popularity of online education, prompting students to strongly advocate for their stance on participating in this form of learning. Several variables, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use of the e-learning system, and considered hurdles, influence this issue (Ajibade et al., 2022). The obstacles and issues pertaining to COVID-19 substantially impact learners' choices to engage in online learning during the pandemic. Conversely, learners' assessment of online learning's worth is subject to the influence of perceived value (Zamani et al., 2022).

The aforementioned study conducted by Kimet al. (2023) has provided evidence to support the notion that perceived utility plays a crucial mediating function in the association between compatibility, comfort, and the effective online education.

H3: Perceived usefulness has a positive impact on worth of online education.

H4: Perceived usefulness mediates the relationship between perceived ease of use and worth of online education.

7. Conceptual frameworks

The conceptual framework of this study was established based on previous research aimed at identifying the determinants that impact individuals' views about the utilisation of online education. A model is constructed by establishing connections and shedding light on each individual factor. The framework is visually depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework (Source: Davis, 1989)

8. Methodology

The current study employed a quantitative methodology to examine several factors that contribute to the formation of perceived ease of use (PEU) and perceived usefulness (PU) concerning the worth of online education (WOE). Therefore, the study's intended audience comprises students, teachers, and lecturers residing in Dhaka city. Dhaka has been chosen as the central region for data collection due to its status as the capital city, which affords it the most significant concentration of educational activities within the nation. The study used convenient sampling which asserted that using convenient sampling enables researchers to purposefully select respondents with a high level of knowledge and proficiency in the subject matter under investigation. According to Zheng & Valente (2023), the optimal range for sample size selection in processing structural equation modelling (SEM) data is between 200 and 400. The present study involved the distribution of 300

sets of questionnaires within various college and universities in Dhaka. A total of 271 replies were collected. After excluding the eleven incomplete items, a total of 265 responses remained that were suitable for analysis.

The research model consists of three dimensions, namely, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and worth of online education. The questionnaire utilised in this study was designed internally and comprised of twelve items. These items were adapted and adjusted as necessary to align with the specific needs and objectives of the current research. The study employed a 5-point Likert scale, as suggested by Hair et al. (2017), with response options ranging from 1, indicating "strongly disagree" to 5, indicating "strongly agree." The questionnaire items were designed in the English language. To ascertain the validity of the items, 20 sets of questionnaires were administered to university teachers as part of a preliminary research phase aimed at gathering their perspectives and recommendations. The questionnaire was revised in response to the feedback and recommendations made by participants to enhance its clarity and comprehensibility. In this study, the statistical data analysis was conducted using SPSS-23. In addition, the AMOS-SEM methodology was employed to validate the measurement model and substantiate the research hypothesis.

9. Result And Analysis

Demographic Profile

Out of the total sample size of 265 participants, 137 individuals were identified as male, accounting for 51.69.4% of the participants, while the remaining 128 individuals were identified as female, constituting 48.30% of the participants. Among the respondents, 63 individuals (23.77%) were in the age range of 24–29, whereas the age group of 54 and above accounted for nineteen responses (7.17%). The age cohort ranging from 48 to 53 years old accounted for 21 individuals, representing a proportion of 7.92%. The age groups ranging from 36 to 41 and 30 to 35 exhibited the second and third most significant response rates, with 53 (20.00%) and 46 (17.36%) participants, respectively. The age cohort ranging from 42 to 47 years old was represented by a total of 24 participants, but the age group spanning from 18 to 23 years old received a higher number of replies, amounting to 39. The survey respondents' occupation status was classified into service holders and students. The poll encompassed 190 students, accounting for 71.69% of the participants. The remaining 28.30% of respondents were individuals employed in the service sector. Seventy-three participants, accounting for 27.55% of the sample, obtained scores between the RM 8,000 and RM 9,000 range. However, seven individuals, accounting for a mere 2.64% of the total sample, reported incomes above RM 10,000. Fifty-four individuals, or 20.37% of the sample, reported an income range between RM 4,000 and RM 5,000. Fifty-one participants reported earning a monthly income from RM 6,000 to RM 7,000. The study conducted on RM 2-3 K revealed that 38 out of 42 respondents belonged to the earning category of less than 2 K. Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Table 1 Demographic profile of respondents

Attributes	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	137	51.69
	Female	128	48.30
Age	18-23	39	14.72
	24-29	63	23.77
	30-35	46	17.36
	36-41	53	20.00
	42-47	24	9.06
	48-53	21	7.92
	54 and above	19	7.17
Occupation	Service	75	28.30
	Student	190	71.69
Family Income	Less than 2 k	42	15.85
	2k-3k	38	14.34
	4k-5k	54	20.37
	6k-7k	51	19.25
	8k-9k	73	27.55
	10 k and above	7	2.64

10. Exploratory Factor Analysis

An exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was performed to examine and establish the relationship between a set of interrelated factors. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure and Bartlett's test of sphericity were employed to commence the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) in this investigation. The KMO test produced a value of 0.691, as presented in Table 2, indicating statistical significance as it was over the 0.50 threshold (Akça & Kurudirek 2023). Bartlett's Test of Sphericity yielded a statistically significant result ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the variables being examined exhibited a substantial correlation. The results of the KMO test and Bartlett's test of sphericity suggest that the dataset was suitable for exploratory factor analysis.

Table 2 KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.691
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1154.736
	Df	36
	Sig.	.000

The study conducted by Akça &Kurudirek (2023) employed exploratory factor analysis, utilizing principal component analysis and the varimax rotation approach. Furthermore, constructs were represented by elements with eigenvalues exceeding 1.0 and factor loadings surpassing 0.50.

It is essential to mention that four components were identified by exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Nevertheless, specific characteristics were excluded from the study due to their tendency to overshadow other variables. As a result of the repeated exclusion of PU4, PEOU3, and WOE3 from the principal component analysis, the components listed in Table 3 demonstrate the ability to load independently without any adverse effects.

Table 3 Total Variance Explained

Rotated Component Matrix ^a			
	Component		
	1	2	3
PU3	.946		
PU2	.937		
PU1	.841		
PEOU1		.894	
PEOU2		.872	
PEOU4		.848	
WOE4			.786
WOE2			.785
WOE1			.617
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.			
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.			
a. Rotation converged in 4 iterations.			

11. Measurement Model

A measurement model was constructed to assess the validity of exogenous and endogenous variables in the fitness-tested model. The dependent variable of this study is the value or worth attributed to online education. However, the exogenous variable pertains to the perceived ease of use. However, it should be noted that perceived utility functioned as a mediator in this context. According to the exploratory factor analysis (EFA), specific components have been excluded from consideration.

Figure 2 Measurement Model

Following the modification illustrated in Figure 2, the variables were subjected to a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), resulting in a Comparative Fit Index (CFI) value of 0.977 and a Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) value of 0.070. These values indicate that the model's fit is deemed satisfactory according to established criteria. The chi-square value obtained in the analysis is 45.735, with a corresponding degree of freedom of 20. The calculated chi-square value of 2.287 is lower than the predetermined threshold value of 5.0. Table 4 presents a concise overview of the measuring model.

Table 4 Summary of Measurement Model Results

Name of Category	Recommended Value	Obtained Value	Comments
Absolute fit	RMSEA ≤ 0.08	0.070	The recommended level is achieved
Incremental fit	CFI ≥ 0.90	0.977	The recommended level is achieved
Parsimonious fit	ChiSq/df ≤ 5	2.287	The recommended level is achieved

The correlation values of both exogenous and endogenous latent variables are below the threshold of 0.85, indicating the presence of discriminant validity among these variables.

12. Testing Reliability and Validity

The present study employed a reliability assessment, which involved using SPSS software to conduct Cronbach's alpha analysis for all constructs. Additionally, AMOS software was employed to measure Construct Reliability (CR). Based on the findings of Tahir (2023) it is recommended that Cronbach's alpha surpass a threshold of 0.60. Table 5 presents the Cronbach's alpha and

composite reliability (CR) values for all constructs that are above the specified minimal threshold. In addition, it is noteworthy that the standardised loadings for all three components surpass the criterion of 0.50. This suggests no concerns regarding the dependability of any of the constructions.

Table 5 Factor Loading, AVE and CR computation for the Constructs.

Constructs	Items	Factor loading	Cronbach α	AVE	CR
PEU	PEU1	.799	0.77	0.71	0.89
	PEU2	.776			
	PEU4	.825			
PU	PU1	.759	0.90	0.53	0.70
	PU2	.883			
	PU3	.896			
WOE	WOE1	.51	0.77	0.75	0.86
	WOE2	.668			
	WOE4	.618			
Overall (9 items)			0.74		

Furthermore, the validity of the three constructs in this study was assessed using the Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) estimations. The findings shown in Table 5 demonstrate that the average variance extracted (AVE) values for the constructs of Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), Perceived Usefulness (PU), and Willingness to Engage (WOE) are 0.71, 0.53 and 0.77, respectively. Convergent validity was successfully established for all components, as evidenced by the composite reliability (CR) values over 0.60 (ranging from 0.70 to 0.89). Based on the findings of Shrestha (2021) and Baistaman et al. (2020), it can be inferred that when the average variance extracted (AVE) is below the threshold of 0.50, however, the composite reliability above 0.60, the construct's convergent validity can still be considered satisfactory. Nevertheless, the present investigation demonstrates that the values of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Composite Reliability (CR) surpass the predetermined threshold level. Therefore, one could claim that the establishment of legitimacy for additional investigation has been achieved.

13. Structural equation modelling

Structural equation modelling (SEM) is a statistical technique used to analyse complex relationships between observed and latent variables. SEM allows researchers to test and estimate the direct and indirect effects.

The improved structural model, as depicted in Figure 3, demonstrates a satisfactory fit with a Comparative Fit Index (CFI) value of 0.972, surpassing the recommended threshold of 0.90. Additionally, the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) value of 0.076 meets the

established standards. The Chi-square value of 2.538, which has been normalised, is found to be less than five. This indicates that the structural model is a good fit. The degrees of freedom associated with this Chi-square value are 21. Additionally, the unnormalised Chi-square value is calculated to be 53.289. Hence, the structural model remains well-suited.

Figure 3: Structural Model

Based on the SEM model (Figure 3), table 6 displays the estimated paths between the constructions.

Table 6 Path Estimation

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Decision
PU	<---	PEOU	0.20	.039	2.121	.034	Supported
WOE	<---	PU	0.32	.067	2.468	.014	Supported
WOE	<---	PEOU	0.89	.054	3.579	***	Supported

14. HYPOTHESIS TESTING

The results obtained from the structural path analysis within the model demonstrate that Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) exerts a statistically significant impact on Perceived Usefulness (PU). According to the data presented in Table 6, the hypothesis testing yielded a standardised regression weight of 0.20, a standard error of 0.039, and a critical ratio of 2.121. Notably, the critical ratio exceeds the threshold value of 1.96. Previous studies have identified a positive correlation between Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU) (Lewis & Sauro, 2023; Amin et al., 2014; Andavara et al., 2021). Hence, the null hypothesis has been refuted, indicating a positive correlation between Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU) in the context of online education.

The analysis of hypotheses (refer to Table 6) revealed that there is a statistically significant relationship between Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Work Outcome Expectancy (WOE). This relationship is supported by a standard regression weight of 0.89, a standard error of 0.054, and a critical ratio of 3.579. Consequently, the process of hypothesis testing demonstrates that perceived ease of use (PEOU) significantly impacts worth of online education (WOE). Given the rejection of the null hypothesis, there exists considerable empirical support, as demonstrated by prior investigations conducted by Amin et al., (2014); Dhingra & Mudgal (2019) and Andavara et al. (2021), indicating a positive relationship between Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Work Outcome Evaluation (WOE).

The statistical analysis of hypothesis three yielded a standardised regression weight of 0.32, with a standard error of 0.067. The critical ratio was determined to be 2.462, and the P value was found to be significant. These results are presented in Table 6. Previous studies have demonstrated the good impact of perceived usefulness and worth of online education, as evidenced by the research conducted by Salloum et al. (2019), Al-Fraihat et al. (2020), and Zalat et al. (2021). This study highlights the importance of the impact of perceived usefulness on the worth of online education. The rejection of the null hypothesis provides evidence supporting the notion that perceived usefulness positively impacts the worth of online education.

15. Mediation effect analysis

According to Hair et al. (2017) mediation is deemed to occur when the product of the indirect pathways loads above a threshold of 0.08. In the present study, the aim was to examine the mediating role of perceived usefulness (PU) in the relationship between perceived ease of use (PEOU) and work outcome effectiveness (WOE). The analysis revealed that the coefficients of the indirect paths were 0.32 and 0.20, indicating the presence of a mediating influence. Hence, the product of 0.32 and 0.20, calculated as 0.064, is shown to be smaller than 0.08.

Table 7 Mediating Path Estimation

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
PU	<---	PEOU	0.20	.039	2.121	.034
WOE	<---	PU	0.32	.067	2.468	.014

Research has demonstrated no significant impact of perceived usefulness on perceived ease of use and worth in the context of online education. Conversely, a significant direct link between these two factors was observed in the present study. Hence, it can be concluded that the perceived usefulness does not mediate the association between the perceived ease of use and the worth of online education.

16. Conclusion and Recommendations

Online education systems have utilised the approach of acquiring knowledge and learning for pupils. It equally exerts a detrimental impact on the holistic development of pupils throughout their educational journey. Adopting an efficient method is necessary to mitigate the harmful impact and sustain uninterrupted online learning to achieve seamless educational outcomes. Wong et al. (2021) suggest that adopting appropriate breaks from online classrooms can yield advantages in mitigating the adverse effects of prolonged screen exposure. According to Ji et al. (2019), implementing efficient scheduling can yield advantages in the administration of academic pursuits. In the present setting, students can create a comprehensive learning calendar that encompasses both online and traditional classrooms to acquire knowledge. With the reopening of educational institutions in the aftermath of the epidemic, students can resume their conventional learning practises by attending in-person classrooms. By adhering to these methods, students can effectively mitigate the negative impact of online education.

The study mentioned above finishes by providing an analysis of online education in terms of its perceived usefulness and ease of use in the learning process. The integration of online education is similarly encompassed within the broader context, aiming to highlight its advantages in upgrading the education system. Likewise, it has entailed articulating the specified aim and objectives for the overarching research endeavour.

Furthermore, the literature study section has identified beneficial and destructive online education elements for students. Simultaneously, a specific conceptual framework has been introduced, illustrating the critical variables of the study. The methodology section has provided a comprehensive discussion of several aspects of the research process, including research philosophies, methodologies, research design, data collection, data analysis, sampling strategy, and ethical considerations. As a result, future researcher can easily comprehend the employed approach in the entirety of the research. Finally, the discovery and examination have successfully

demonstrated the survey outcomes, bolstered by using SPSS and SEM. Hence, it is acknowledged that the perceived level of ease associated with online education surpasses the perceived level of usefulness attributed to online education.

This research only used primary data. It is advisable to incorporate secondary data to give qualitative data or information about the research issue. Including and presenting an alternative perspective on the research issue holds equal potential for further investigation. Therefore, including both primary and secondary research methodologies will enhance the presentation of a comprehensive understanding with detailed insights about the research subject.

The government should actively encourage the implementation of an online education system to ensure a harmonious coexistence with the traditional education system. The rationale behind this is that it will enhance online education's perceived usefulness among learners, facilitating effective learning. However, this approach will facilitate the provision of a continuous and adaptable learning experience for pupils, enabling them to remain competitive in the field of education.

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